

ISic0870

I.Sicily inscription 0870

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

03.10.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 27

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140348

1. Φουρία χρηστὰ καὶ ἄμενπτος
2. χαῖρε, ἔζησεν ἔτη λα'.
- 3.

Edition: PHI175465

1. Φουρία χρηστὰ καὶ ἄμεμπτος
2. χαῖρε. ἔζησε ἔτη λδ'.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492498

EDCS 39102024

PHI 140348

PHI 175465

Bibliography

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